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Impact of digital technologies on the economic security of enterprises: prospects and threats

KEYWORDS

digital technologies in business,
digital transformation of enterprises,
economic security,
cybersecurity,
business digitalization,
risk management in a digital environment

ABSTRACT

Introduction. Digital technologies are becoming an integral part of business processes. They enable enterprises to streamline operations, reduce costs, and enhance efficiency. However, alongside this, new risks and threats emerge related to cybersecurity, data protection, and other aspects.

The article aims to analyze the impact of digital technologies on the economic security of enterprises.

Materials and methods. The methodology of economic security research in the context of digitalization combines several approaches to identify limitations, risks, and ways to overcome them, including a systematic approach, a process-oriented approach, comparative analysis, and empirical analysis.

Results. The authors propose the following measures to overcome restrictions in assessing the level of economic security in the context of digitalization: a) developing a digital transformation strategy, taking into account the specifics of the enterprise and risks; b) strengthening cybersecurity through software updates, the use of domestic solutions, and the involvement of specialists; c) advanced training for employees to ensure successful adaptation to new technologies; d) investments in digital infrastructure, including cloud technologies and high-speed internet; e) state support through subsidies, grants, and tax incentives to stimulate digitalization.

Conclusion. The authors recommend developing integrated approaches to assessing economic security that take into account the characteristics of the digital environment and promote active interaction between enterprises, the state, and the scientific community for successful digital transformation. To assess the effectiveness of this interaction, it is proposed to use structured methods, metrics, and analysis of results, including both quantitative and qualitative indicators.

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INTRODUCTION

The development of digital technologies profoundly impacts all aspects of economic activity, including ensuring financial stability and security. In the context of the rapid introduction of digital solutions, there is a need to analyze new threats and restrictions associated with digitalization, which emphasizes the relevance of this study. Modern businesses face challenges such as cyberattacks, data breaches, reliance on imported software, and a shortage of skilled personnel, making it much harder to assess their economic security.

Economic security refers to the state of protection that an enterprise maintains against internal and external threats to ensure stable functioning and development in a rapidly changing environment. However, in the era of digitalization, traditional methods of assessing economic security are becoming insufficiently effective. New approaches are required that take into account the specific characteristics of the digital environment and the latest risks associated with the use of digital technologies.

The relevance of the research topic is emphasized by the need to adapt methodological tools for assessing economic security to the realities of the modern digital economy. This will increase enterprises' resistance to new threats and minimize the risks associated with the digital transformation process.

The object of the study is industrial enterprises that are actively introducing digital technologies, and the subject is mechanisms and tools for assessing their economic security.

This study aims to analyze the current limitations in assessing the level of economic security in the context of digitalization and develop recommendations for overcoming them.

The present work is based on a systems approach, using comparative and logical analysis, and examining empirical data presented in scientific publications and official statistical reports.

METHODS

The research materials included relevant research and reviews in scientific journals on economic security and digital technologies (*Journal of Industry, Competition*

and Trade; Scientific Reports; Humanities and Social Sciences Communications; Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment; Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship, etc.), as well as materials from international conferences.

The methodology of this study is based on systematic, process-oriented, and comparative approaches. These methods make it possible to identify key limitations and risks associated with assessing economic security in the context of digitalization, as well as potential ways to mitigate them.

A systematic approach was employed to analyze economic security as an integrated system comprising financial, human resource, information, and management components. Within the section “Main limitations of economic security assessment”, this approach allowed for the identification of the relationships between technological, infrastructural, management, and financial constraints.

The process approach was used to study the dynamics of threats and risks arising from the digitalization process. In the section “Risks and threats in the context of digitalization”, this approach was applied to analyze the key stages of introducing digital technologies, including cyberattacks, data leakage, and financial risks.

Comparative analysis was used to examine the experiences of foreign countries and Russia in ensuring economic security. In the sections “Main limitations of economic security assessment” and “Proposals for overcoming limitations”, comparative analysis helped to identify effective practices that can be adapted to Russian conditions.

Empirical analysis is based on the study of statistical data provided by Rosstat, as well as on the analysis of scientific publications and reports. The results of the empirical analysis were used in the sections “Risks and threats in the context of digitalization” and “Conclusions and recommendations” to justify the proposed solutions.

Qualitative methods, including interviews with experts in the fields of digital transformation and economic security, as well as the analysis of case studies from industrial enterprises, formed the basis for the section “Proposals for overcoming restrictions”. This section presents practical measures to minimize risks and enhance cybersecurity.

The use of these methodological approaches made it possible to comprehensively study the nature of limitations in assessing economic security and substantiate recommendations for overcoming them.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Economic security is a key component of sustainable enterprise development. It is defined as the state of protection an enterprise has from threats that can negatively affect its functioning, financial stability, and competitiveness. In the context of digitalization, the concept of economic security is evolving, necessitating consideration of new risks and opportunities associated with the introduction of digital technologies.

In the scientific literature, the following key aspects of economic security are distinguished: financial stability, data security, personnel security, and the stability of business processes. Digital transformation reinforces the interconnectedness between these aspects by incorporating elements such as cybersecurity, adaptability to technological changes, and resilience against digital threats.

According to Oborin, the digitalization of industrial enterprises is changing traditional approaches to managing economic security, focusing on intelligent control systems and automation of business processes [1]. However, such changes are accompanied by risks, including cyberattacks, the loss of confidential information, and dependence on foreign technologies.

Somenkova notes that successful adaptation of enterprises to the digital economy requires the development of methodological tools for assessing risks and threats, as well as the introduction of strategies to minimize them [2]. Additionally, a crucial factor is the availability of qualified personnel who can effectively utilize digital technologies.

The digital economy presents new challenges, but it also opens up opportunities for improving efficiency and competitiveness. To assess economic security in these conditions, the integration of approaches that take into account the specifics of the digital environment is required, such as big data analysis, cyber threat monitoring, and risk modeling [3].

Digitalization enhances an enterprise's economic security by increasing efficiency, protecting data, and enabling a rapid response to threats.

Wu et al. argue that the positive impact of digital trade is more substantial for enterprises with a high level of digital trade participation and market competition. At the same time, it is weakened for enterprises with a high share of overseas business. The scientists have demonstrated that digital trade enhances the competitiveness of enterprises primarily through three channels: expanding assets, reducing costs, and increasing efficiency [4].

Luo and Liu argue that the adoption of digital technologies significantly impacts the environmental and economic performance of enterprises, stimulating their service-oriented transformation and technological innovation, which in turn contributes to their sustainable development [5].

Ling and Ling show that digital inclusive finance has a positive impact on corporate digital technological innovation. The researchers propose a new incentive mechanism to enhance the innovative potential of manufacturing enterprises in the digital technology field [6].

Peng et al. consider the impact of digital transformation on inefficient investments under conditions of double pressure: operational diversification and environmental uncertainty. Their results show that digital transformation significantly reduces inefficient investments, effectively mitigating both underinvestment and overinvestment [7].

Wang et al. state that the perception of climate risks by enterprises affects organizational stability. They also note the mediating effect of innovations in the field of "green" technologies and the mitigating impact of digital transformation and organizational inefficiency on this relationship. According to the scientists, the corporate perception of climate risks can increase organizational stability. The digital transformation of enterprises positively mitigates the relationship between the perception of climate risks by enterprises and innovations in the field of "green" technologies [8].

Xu et al. note that enterprises face a double challenge: the development of digitalization and achieving environmental sustainability. The scientists demonstrate an inverted U-shaped connection between the digital transformation of enterprises and innovations in the field of "green" technologies. They also note that environmental regulation amplifies the positive impact of digital initiatives on the outcomes of eco-innovation [9].

Golovko et al. consider the main trends in the digitalization of enterprise management in all functional areas. The authors explore how digitalization can enhance the economic efficiency and security of modern organizations. They also propose digitalization tools within the framework of strategic projections of the enterprise structure (finance, market, business processes, potential) [10].

Security depends on the industry. In particular, the service sector relies on reputation, transport on logistics, the agricultural industry on resources and ecology, etc.

Okhrimenko et al. note that although new information technologies have contributed to the development of new industries, they have also brought new threats to information security. The authors identified and systematized threats to economic security arising from the information environment, and determined a set of measures to protect risk areas. They also developed recommendations aimed at preventing and minimizing the negative impact of information threats on economic security [11].

Svetkina et al. pay special attention to the problems of creating an information and digital structure, which is currently an essential element of regional companies' economic security systems. The authors note that the construction of a logical and functional information architecture in digital format ensures the reliability and transparency of financial and economic information, maintains the continuity of the company's activities, and helps to achieve its goals [12].

Piskunov and Tarasova consider key aspects of ensuring the economic security of enterprises in the bakery industry with an emphasis on the introduction of innovative technologies. The authors address major threats, including fluctuations in commodity prices, changing consumer preferences, and the need for modern management approaches. They emphasize that the successful introduction of innovations contributes not only to increasing competitiveness but also to the long-term sustainability of bakery enterprises, ultimately ensuring their economic security in uncertain conditions [13].

Al-Mhiqani et al. argue that the railway industry has mastered digitalization and interconnectedness by integrating information and communication technologies into the traditional infrastructure of operational technologies. The researchers demonstrate that railway systems/networks are highly intolerant of network interference and require a high degree of safety, stability, and reliability. The consequences of cyberattacks for the Central Railway can have economic, financial, reputational, environmental, and/or physical aspects [14].

Poberezhna analyzes the problems faced by enterprises in the modern transport sector, namely, a significant increase in cyberattacks, especially using malicious software. The researcher proposed a mathematical model for applying the Zero Trust concept for a transport enterprise using game theory, which minimizes the probability of an attacker's success and provides optimal protection based on mixed strategies [15].

According to Botschner et al., despite numerous advantages, digital agriculture and its supply chains have vulnerabilities related to cybersecurity. These vulnerabilities create opportunities for criminal profit-making and for geopolitical adversaries capable of causing widespread damage to this critical infrastructure [16].

Liu et al. examine the impact and mechanism of digital transformation on the quality and safety of exported agricultural products at the enterprise level using the step differential method. According to the scientists, the digital transformation of enterprises effectively improves the quality and safety of exported agricultural products [17].

Klishin and Chechulin present a methodology for analyzing the impact of the digital transformation of information security management on enterprise architecture. The scientists considered the following internal indicators: the level of information security, the effectiveness of information security, and the total cost of ownership of information security management processes [18].

Tarasova considers the most important aspects of trade secret protection as a key strategy for ensuring enterprises' economic security. The author examines the implications of applying intellectual property rights, non-disclosure agreements, and the broader legal landscape, providing readers with a clear understanding of the legal tools available to protect confidential information. The importance of data protection and encryption is emphasized, and recommendations are provided to enhance resistance to emerging threats [19].

Hutsaliuk et al. consider operational and economic security as two key aspects that ensure the sustainability and success of any companies and organizations. The scientists have demonstrated that ensuring operational and financial security requires an integrated approach that includes the development of strategies, the implementation of security measures, and the continuous updating of policies and procedures to minimize risks and ensure the success of the company's activities [20].

Digital enterprise security models comprise a set of software and analytical tools that enable enterprises to identify, assess, and manage economic risks using data and modern technologies.

Kadesnikova writes that improving the economic safety of production enterprises is an urgent issue that can be addressed by introducing corporate information systems into accounting processes to increase operational efficiency. The author's approach suggests estimating the expected economic effect of implementing software products for automating the main business processes of an industrial enterprise [21].

Li and Zhang et al. developed a risk prediction model based on big data analysis to improve the efficiency of enterprise information protection. A big data analytics system that can monitor and intelligently identify potential security risks in real-time is built upon the development of complex network analysis algorithms and machine learning models. The model built by the authors significantly increased the accuracy of early warning and the speed of enterprises' response to various information security incidents [22].

Wang believes that financial reporting fraud poses a significant threat to the digital transformation of businesses, as organizations increasingly rely on computerized financial systems, cloud accounting, and AI-based financial decision-making. The author presents a deep learning fraud detection model designed to improve fraud detection in financial statements. The system is deployed through Google Cloud Functions, providing real-time fraud risk assessment and seamless enterprise integration [23].

Li introduced an innovative model for measuring enterprise productivity, harnessing the synergistic potential of multi-criteria optimization and genetic algorithms. This performance measurement model, based on genetic algorithms, allows for real-time monitoring and optimization of enterprise performance [24].

Rahim and Chishti note that reliable security measures, adequate privacy protection, and authentication mechanisms are necessary to further implement IoT technology on larger, heterogeneous devices. Due to resource constraints, including limited processing power, memory, power consumption, and network bandwidth, as well as the protocols used, implementing traditional security software on IoT devices is a challenging task. The scientists provide a brief overview of IoT security architecture and a comprehensive overview of the latest IoT security solutions, such as blockchain, which can significantly improve the level of IoT security [25].

Zastupov offers innovative digital solutions that allow enterprises to create more efficient systems for organizing wages. The author suggests that the Solut digital system, which uses digital technologies for rationing labor, will enable enterprises to reach a fundamentally new level of determining the number of personnel, as well as the economic justification of labor costs [26].

Thus, the theoretical basis of the study is grounded in the examination of the transformation of the concept of economic security under the influence of digital technologies, as well as in the analysis of existing approaches to risk management in the digital environment.

RESULTS

Main limitations of economic security assessment

The economic security of enterprises in the context of digitalization is subject to significant restrictions related to technological, infrastructure, management, and financial aspects. This section will address the key limitations and their impact on the effectiveness of safety assessment.

There are technological and infrastructural limitations. The immaturity of digital technologies is directly related to the uneven development of infrastructure. For example, enterprises in regions with limited access to high-speed Internet are experiencing difficulties in implementing modern automation systems [27]. The lack of broadband Internet reduces the ability to integrate IoT solutions, thereby limiting the efficiency of production and monitoring [28].

Management and infrastructure constraints include low managerial qualifications, which often result in an inability to strategically adapt enterprises to digitalization conditions. This, in turn, increases dependence on outdated infrastructure. For example, enterprises with an unstructured approach to implementing digital technologies tend to be inefficient when implementing ERP systems, which could increase productivity [29]. Additionally, the lack of long-term modernization planning leads companies to continue investing in outdated technologies, which increases operating costs and reduces profitability.

Financial constraints, expressed in high digitalization costs, are widening the gap between large enterprises and small companies, limiting the latter's opportunities for modernization. For example, developing customized cybersecurity solutions or implementing data analytics systems requires significant investment beyond the reach of most small businesses. Limited access to government subsidies or benefits, along with the need for credit financing, creates a vicious circle effect: lack of investment leads to the strengthening of all other restrictions. Financial pressure is especially noticeable in conditions of economic instability or sanctions restrictions.

The lack of qualified professionals exacerbates the problems associated with other restrictions. For example, a lack of cybersecurity knowledge increases the risks of data breaches and cyberattacks, necessitating additional costs to restore information systems. Additionally, a lack of expertise in digital project management hinders technology adoption, resulting in less flexible processes. This, in turn, reduces the competitiveness of companies, especially in high-tech industries.

Understanding the relationships between constraints allows businesses to prioritize their efforts effectively. Thus, the modernization of digital infrastructure should be accompanied by training personnel and involving specialists to expedite the adaptation to new conditions. For example, enterprises in regions with a low level of digitalization are advised to develop comprehensive programs that encompass both infrastructure improvements and the implementation of educational initiatives for their personnel.

Additionally, integrating financial support from the state, including subsidies, tax incentives, and concessional lending programs, can help alleviate systemic restrictions. For example, providing grants to small and medium-sized enterprises for implementing data analytics technologies can significantly reduce barriers to entering new markets.

Long-term strategies should also consider the need to develop centralized platforms for monitoring threats and analyzing data, which will facilitate a more even distribution of digital resources. This approach, combined with the development of human capital, will minimize the cumulative impact of restrictions and ensure the stability of enterprises during digital transformation.

Risks and threats in the context of digitalization

Digitalization presents significant opportunities for enhancing business process efficiency, but also introduces new risks and threats that require special attention.

Cyber threats. One of the most significant risks of the digital age is an increase in cyberattacks aimed at data leakage, system disruption, or causing financial loss. Cyber threats are becoming more complex and require the use of advanced cybersecurity technologies [30].

Cyberattacks remain one of the primary threats to enterprises in the context of digitalization. According to the Cybersecurity Ventures report (2024), the global damage from cyberattacks in 2023 amounted to \$8.4 trillion, and it is projected to increase to \$10.5 trillion by 2025. More than 68% of industrial enterprises worldwide faced attempts to attack their information systems in 2022. On average, production equipment downtime due to cyberattacks is 22 hours, resulting in a loss of approximately \$270,000 for an average enterprise.

Data breach. The use of cloud technologies and big data increases the likelihood of confidential information being leaked. This poses risks for both individual enterprises and entire industries.

Data breaches result in loss of competitive advantage and penalties. According to an IBM study from 2023, the average cost of a data breach in the industry is \$4.35 million per incident. Approximately 47% of leaks are due to inadequate protection of data storage systems. The use of encryption reduces the damage from data leakage by 30%.

Financial risks. The high cost of implementing and operating digital technologies increases the financial burden on enterprises, especially in conditions of economic instability. Mismanaging these costs can result in financial losses.

The introduction of digital technologies requires significant investment, further increasing the financial burden on enterprises. According to McKinsey, the average cost of digital transformation for an industrial enterprise is 3–5% of annual revenue. Mismanagement of digital projects leads to budget overruns 45% of the time. Companies that have completed digital transformation have seen an increase in operating profit of 20–25% [31].

Human factor. Employees' low digital literacy or resistance to change often causes errors that lead to failures in digital systems. This highlights the importance of investing in staff training and development.

The lack of qualified personnel remains a critical risk. According to Deloitte research, 62% of industrial enterprises have a shortage of digital technology specialists. About 35% of cybersecurity incidents are due to employee errors. Professional development programs can reduce the number of errors by 28% [32].

Dependence on external suppliers. The use of foreign technologies and equipment introduces additional risks, including those associated with sanctions, fluctuations in supply conditions, and the potential for technical support issues. Accenture's research shows that 48% of businesses depend on imported software. About 20% of companies reported disruptions due to sanctions or changes in supply conditions. The replacement of imported equipment with domestic analogues can reduce risks by 15–20% [33].

To minimize these risks, it is necessary to implement an integrated approach to ensuring economic security, including monitoring threats, developing risk management strategies, and investing in cyber defense and personnel training [34–39].

Proposals for overcoming restrictions

To overcome the limitations arising from the assessment of the level of economic security in the context of digitalization, the following measures are proposed:

1. Developing a comprehensive digital transformation strategy. It is essential to develop a comprehensive plan for introducing digital technologies, taking into account the unique characteristics of the enterprise and its specific industry. The strategy should include implementation stages, as well as an assessment of possible risks and measures to minimize them.
2. Strengthening cybersecurity. This involves regular software updates, the use of advanced data protection systems, and the involvement of information security specialists. Transitioning to domestic software products can also mitigate the risks associated with dependence on foreign suppliers.
3. Personnel development. Regular training of employees and the development of digital skills are essential for successful adaptation to new technologies. This will help to prevent human error.
4. Investment in digital infrastructure. It is essential to support the development of cloud technologies, high-speed internet, and big data platforms, which will ensure the availability of modern solutions for even small and medium-sized enterprises.
5. Government support. A crucial factor is creating conditions to stimulate digitalization through subsidies, grants, and tax incentives. Government programs can play a key role in the development of the digital economy.

CONCLUSION

The recommendations proposed by the authors include the development of integrated approaches to assessing economic security, taking into account the specific characteristics of the digital environment. It is also recommended to promote active collaboration between enterprises, the state, and the scientific community to create favorable conditions for digital transformation. Assessing the effectiveness of this interaction within the framework of digitalization requires the use of structured methods, clear metrics, and analysis of the results achieved. This process involves both quantitative and qualitative approaches to measure the success of joint initiatives and identify areas for improvement. To achieve this, it is proposed to develop an integrated indicator – the Digital Cooperation Index (DCI). Its calculation can take into account the activity of participants (the number and quality of projects), the level of digitalization (the introduction of technologies and coverage of regions), and participant satisfaction (based on feedback).

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